

Developmental biology and host plant range of rice ear-cutting caterpillar *Mythimna separata* (Walker)

J. L. A. Catindig and A. T. Barrion, IRRI; and J. A. Litsinger, 1365 Jacobs Place, Dixon, CA 95620, USA

Forty-one common ricefield plants from families Poaceae (25), Cyperaceae (6), Commelinaceae (3), Leguminosae (3), and one each from Amaranthaceae, Pontederiaceae, Portulacaceae, and Onagraceae were evaluated as host plants to *M. separata*.

Ten unfed newly emerged larvae from a culture maintained on rice in a greenhouse were placed on a 25- to 30-d-old test plant in a 20-cm-diam clay pot within a 10- × 72-cm cylindrical mylar cage with side and top nylon mesh (1 mm²) vents. Each cage was a treatment. Host suitability was determined by percentage of larval survival to pupation, larval developmental period, and number of eggs laid/female. The no-choice experiment was replicated 10 times in a

randomized complete block design conducted in a greenhouse where temperature averaged 26.7 ± 0.9 °C and relative humidity, 72.4 ± 4.5%.

Ovipositional preference and fecundity were also determined in a no-choice experiment. Two 3- to 5-d-old pupae reared on rice were placed in a larval developmental cage as described above. Honey solution (10%) in a cotton mesh provided food for the moths.

Thirty-one plant species supported complete larval development (Table 1). Larval survival to pupation was highest on *Leptochloa chinensis* (58%), *Isachne globosa* (54%), *Paspalum paspalodes* (53%), and rice (51%). Larval survival was not higher (<80%) due to mold infections. Larval development was shortest on rice (19.2 d), which was significantly shorter than on *L. chinensis* (21.7 d). Development was longest on *Imperata cylindrica* (34.8 d) and *Brachiaria distachya* (37.8 d).

All 41 species were accepted as ovipositional hosts. Preference was rice > *Paspalum scrobiculatum* > *Digitaria*

ciliaris > *P. paspalodes* > *Leersia hexandra* > *I. globosa*. Females laid the fewest eggs on *Commelina diffusa*, mungbean, *Dactyloctenium aegyptium*, and *Ludwigia octovalvis*.

Moths laid smooth, shiny yellowish-white spherical eggs in rows. On rice, egg incubation lasted 3 d and larvae passed five stadia in 20 d (Table 2). Prepupation lasted 2.0 d and pupation, 8.3 d. Total development from egg to adult emergence was 30.2 d and female longevity was 10.8 d. Fecundity was 220 ± 59.6 eggs/female.

M. separata larvae, although polyphagous, showed incomplete development on 10 species: three in Poaceae, two in Commelinaceae, and one each in Leguminosae, Amaranthaceae, Pontederiaceae, Portulacaceae, and Onagraceae (Table 1). Overall host ranking was rice > *L. chinensis* > *P. paspalodes* > *P. conjugatum* > *E. colona*. ■

Table 1. Comparative developmental biology of *M. separata* on 41 plants.^a IRRI greenhouse, May-Mar 1990.

Host	Parameter				Overall average ranking ^d	
	Nymphal survival (%) ^b		Nymphal duration (d) ^c			Eggs laid (no./5 females)
Poaceae						
Rice TN1	51.0 ± 1.5	ab	19.2 ± 0.8	a	220.0 ± 59.6	1
<i>Leptochloa chinensis</i> (L.) Nees	58.0 ± 19.3	a	21.7 ± 0.8	ab	76.9 ± 3.8	2
<i>Paspalum paspalodes</i> (= <i>P. distichum</i> L.)	53.0 ± 18.9	ab	26.8 ± 2.6	ef	135.0 ± 16.9	3
<i>P. conjugatum</i> Berg.	31.0 ± 3.2	cde	22.2 ± 0.9	bc	45.4 ± 9.3	4
<i>Echinochloa colona</i> (L.) Link	47.0 ± 13.4	ab	27.9 ± 0.7	fh	73.0 ± 86.4	5
<i>Isachne globosa</i> (Thunb.) O. K.	54.0 ± 19.0	a	30.7 ± 1.2	i-k	121.3 ± 58.6	6
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i> (L.) Beauv. ssp. <i>hispidula</i> (Retz.) Honda	42.0 ± 18.7	bc	29.2 ± 1.1	h-k	34.5 ± 13.0	7
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L.) Pers.	33.0 ± 24.1	cd	27.6 ± 1.4	f-h	5.8 ± 4.4	8
Maize	30.0 ± 11.6	def	26.9 ± 0.7	fg	10.5 ± 5.3	9
<i>Eleusine indica</i> Gaertn.	33.0 ± 13.4	d-i	25.0 ± 0.9	cd	29.4 ± 8.4	10
<i>Echinochloa glabrescens</i> Munro ex Hook f.	31.0 ± 15.3	cde	29.7 ± 1.0	h-k	50.1 ± 15.5	11
<i>Chloris barbata</i> Sw.	26.0 ± 14.5	d-g	29.1 ± 0.9	g-j	79.3 ± 55.7	12
<i>Digitaria ciliaris</i> (Retz.) Koel.	23.0 ± 21.6	d-i	27.7 ± 1.0	f-h	143.7 ± 53.0	13
<i>Leersia hexandra</i> Sw.	19.0 ± 12.0	e-j	27.9 ± 0.7	f-h	124.6 ± 19.1	14
<i>Digitaria sanguinalis</i> (L.) Scop.	15.0 ± 9.7	g-k	26.0 ± 2.0	de	21.8 ± 9.7	15
<i>Eriochloa procerata</i> (Retz.) C. E. Hubb.	16.0 ± 5.2	g-j	32.0 ± 0.9	j-l	21.8 ± 10.7	16
<i>Paspalum scrobiculatum</i> L.	30.0 ± 17.0	def	36.4 ± 0.7	m	154.0 ± 61.1	18
<i>Dactyloctenium aegyptium</i> (L.) Beauv.	13.0 ± 4.8	h-m	29.0 ± 0.7	fi	1.7 ± 1.1	22
<i>Triticum aestivum</i> L. em. Thell.	24.0 ± 18.4	d-h	29.0 ± 1.3	cd	43.4 ± 23.9	23
<i>Paspalidium flavidum</i> (Retz.) A. Cameron	2.0 ± 0.3	l-n	32.0 ± 1.5	j-l	58.9 ± 41.4	24
<i>Brachiaria distachya</i> (L.) Stapf.	3.0 ± 2.8	k-n	37.8 ± 0.8	n	62.1 ± 34.5	26

continued on next page

Table 1 continued

Host	Parameter								Overall average ranking ^d
	Nymphal survival (%) ^b		Nymphal duration (d) ^c		Eggs laid (no./5 females)				
<i>Imperata cylindrica</i> (L.) Beauv.	1.0	± 0.2 mn	34.8	± 1.6 l	22.2	± 13.2 k-o			26
<i>Panicum repens</i> L.	0	n	0	0	4.3	± 9.3 no			27
<i>Brachiaria mutica</i> (Forsk.) Stapf.	0	n	0	0	65.8	± 10.8 d-h			28
<i>Bambusa</i> sp.	0	n	0	0	21.4	± 10.2 k-o			29
Cyperaceae									
<i>Cyperus iria</i> L.	30.0	± 14.1 def	27.9	± 1.1 f-h	26.6	± 17.1 j-o			11
<i>C. rotundus</i> L.	18.0	± 15.5 f-j	28.2	± 0.9 f-h	28.0	± 19.1 i-o			17
<i>C. kyllingia</i> Endl.	14.0	± 5.2 h-l	28.3	± 1.4 f-h	43.3	± 19.0 g-m			19
<i>C. difformis</i> L.	8.0	± 6.3 j-n	29.5	± 1.6 h-k	15.8	± 8.9 l-o			20
<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i> (L.)	3.0	± 2.8 k-n	33.8	± 0.8 kl	36.7	± 23.2 h-n			25
<i>Cyperus brevifolius</i> (Rottb.) Hassk.	27.0	± 16.4 d-g	31.0	± 0.8 i-k	85.8	± 44.1 d			30
Commelinaceae									
<i>Commelina diffusa</i> Burm. f.	11.0	± 3.2 i-n	28.9	± 0.6 fi	7.8	± 4.7 no			21
<i>Murdannia nudiflora</i> (L.)	0	n	0	0	19.8	± 9.0 k-o			29
<i>Commelina benghalensis</i> L.	0	n	0	0	12.4	± 9.6 l-o			33
Leguminosae									
Soybean	1.0	± 0.5 mn	29.7	± 1.1 h-k	18.9	± 17.0 k-o			22
Mungbean	1.0	± 0.7 mn	30.8	± 0.9 i-k	2.1	± 2.6 no			25
Cowpea	0	n	0	0	24.0	± 16.5 k-o			29
Amaranthaceae									
<i>Amaranthus spinosus</i> L.	0	n	0	0	30.9	± 16.2 i-o			29
Pontederiaceae									
<i>Monochoria vaginalis</i> (Burm. f.) Presl.	0	n	0	0	14.1	± 4.6 l-o			32
Portulacaceae									
<i>Portulaca oleraceae</i> L.	0	n	0	0	10.3	± 3.3 mno			31
Onagraceae									
<i>Ludwigia octovalvis</i> (Jacq.) Raven	0	n	0	0	1.1	± 1.00			34
CV (%)	66.4		66.5		66.6				
LSD (0.1)	36.7		13.9		0.6				
LSD (0.5)	27.9		10.6		0.5				

^a Av of 10 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different (P <0.01) by LSD statistical test.

^b survival (%) = $\frac{\text{Larvae pupating (no.)}}{\text{Total larvae (no.)}} \times 100$. ^c n = 10. ^d 1 = best, 34 = worst.

Table 2. Life history of *M. separata*.^a IRRRI greenhouse, May-Mar 1990.

	X ± SD
Egg incubation (d)	3.0 ± 0.4
Larval stadium (d)	
I	3.4 ± 0.7
II	3.2 ± 0.4
III	4.0 ± 0.7
IV	4.4 ± 0.5
V	4.9 ± 0.3
Prepupa (d)	2.0 ± 0
Pupa (d)	8.3 ± 0.7
Total developmental period (d)	30.2 ± 2.0
Moth longevity (d)	10.8 ± 2.8
Eggs laid (no./female)	220.0 ± 59.6

^a n = 10.

Integrated pest management — weeds

Weed species in rice seedling nurseries in Kafr El-Sheikh governorate, Egypt

S. M. Hassan, Rice Research and Training Center (RRTC), and A. N. Rao, IRRRI/Egypt, RRTC, Sakha, Kafr El-Sheikh, Egypt

We surveyed weeds in farmers' rice seedling nurseries in Kafr El-Sheikh governorate in Egypt during 1992 summer season.

Twenty species belonging to 13 genera and 9 families were recorded in 30 nurseries. Grasses and broad-leaved weeds accounted for 74% of the species (see table). Those occurring most commonly were *Cyperus difformis*, *Echinochloa crus-galli*, *Ammannia baccifera*, *E. colona*, *E. oryzoides*, and *Dinebra retroflexa*.

All of the farmers surveyed hand weeded the nurseries, achieving 50-70%